

Grappling with Governance: Confronting Government through Graphic Novels

AP Seminar

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Abstract

Marginalization is an incredibly present problem in our world today and there are many ways to fight it. While it may seem like something small, media has always had a large impact.

Understanding institutions to be self-perpetuating organizations valued for their own sake and power to be the ability to impose one's will on another, there is a clear depiction of real-world problems in a very unreal world. This paper will explore how graphic novels add commentary and teach lessons about government and the world we live in by operating in the world of the fantastical.

Keywords: Comic Books, Graphic Novels, Governance, Institutional Power, Marginalization, Media Analysis, Media Studies

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Marginalization is a topic that is increasingly relevant as polarization grows incredibly common in the United States, leading these groups to be further disadvantaged in society. The popular mode for this has historically been through literature and the arts, as these fields allow for raw and authentic portrayals of the suffering that many groups have been made to confront. From stories such as Spiegelman's *Maus* to Marvel's Krakoa era, graphic novels have a unique space in media in that they bridge the gap between varied forms of media and depict stories of courage, similar to Simone Biles when she stepped down from gymnastics according to lead columnist Marcus Thompson, in a way that no other media truly can (Thompson, 2021). As metaphors rage in the colorful (or purposefully colorless) worlds of comic-based media, the forefront of importance is ensuring that these stories have the impact intended and clarify their lessons as influential teachers. Graphic novels' portrayal of marginalization within a political system act as an effective lesson. This lesson is taught repeatedly and relentlessly, proving that political wisdom may very well be inseparable from the genre as a whole, as shown by the prevalent depictions of institutional power, the struggle of rising up, and eventual liberation.

Rising Action

It is common knowledge that there must always be an antagonistic figure in any sort of story. Whether this be one's self, a singular other, or society, this figure frames the story in such a fashion that draws intrigue, and often offers a story *beyond* the story being outright told. This is the case for nearly all media, especially those which find their basis in fiction. For example, *Confrontation on the Bridge*, is a painting that depicts much more than it originally illustrates. Though abstract, the colors, motifs, and framing of the art depict an innate form of fear that one may not be able to fully distinguish at first glance (Lawrence, n.d.). The themes present the harsh

reality of institutionalized prejudice. Perhaps the most notable example of this is found within the dog, an animal often trained to respond harshly to those deemed punishable. Unfortunately, prejudice deems this to often be people of color, specifically African Americans. The dog specifically symbolizes prejudice and marginalization as it depicts police brutality, which is an example of an institution using its power in unrighteous fashion. Though this is a very raw representation of the undeniable possibilities of racism, it is not the everyday case for most individuals of color, nor is it an incredibly relatable or palatable truth for the younger generation. Similarly, Kamala Khan, a young Pakistani-American Muslim teen from the beloved state of New Jersey, represents much more than herself, showing the truth of intersectionality and its ups and downs in a profound fashion. In fact, she managed to show how being Pakistani-American impacts her in her life, allowing her to display her culture and her *heroism*, a type of character that is often avoided in many other facets of media, even today. For example, in *Ms. Marvel: The New Mutant*, written by two Pakistani authors, there are many moments where her intersectionality is the focal point, such as her argument that she is a “Pakistani-American-Inhu-Mutant,” and that she is “walking *proof* that we can all coexist,” invoking the in-universe species of ‘Inhumans’ and ‘Mutants,’ two commonly used extended metaphors within graphic novels that are designed to portray marginalization (Vellani & Pirzada, 2024). This also ties back to the narrative of integration versus separatism, where *coexistence* is highlighted as key. Not all stories, though, are meant for the younger generation. This is also the case for Pulitzer Prize-winning *Maus*, a well-known, practically quintessential example of the fluidity of the genre of graphic novels. Written by a Polish Jew about his father, a Holocaust survivor, and translated into over a dozen languages, the story was created as a means to both put the horrors of the event on display and to confront the trauma of the event itself. The story

frames Jews as mice to German cats and Polish pigs, providing a pivotal and striking story that sharply depicts the darkest tales of humanity (Spiegelman, 2003). The story goes into depth about what it is to reflect and to prevent, as the author and his father are able to reflect upon their past struggles and argue for future prevention in hopes that such a governmental institution does not weaponize their power in such a way again.

Climax

The sharp twists in this world we share are perhaps marked in eras of what one may wish to call ‘goods’ and ‘bads.’ Franklin D. Roosevelt’s *Inaugural Address*, is a prime example of this phenomena, discussing the Great Depression. His adamance to find a solution to what seemed like an impossible problem to solve echoes the striking *hope* that humanity is able to find in devastating times such as this (Roosevelt, 1933). The time period in which F.D.R. headed his New Deal, policies that pushed back against economic discrimination, is a resounding display of the struggle of rising up against previously systematic struggles that had made economic stability difficult. F.D.R.’s speech signaled a massive change in the norm, as did Charles Xavier’s. While the two have vastly different personalities and backgrounds, both of their words helped to instill a sense of *hope* into their people. *House of X/Powers of X*, written by revolutionary writer Jonathan Hickman, two interconnected comic runs from 2019, depict the historical reinventing of mutant politics within the main Marvel Comics continuity, Earth 616. Within it, Charles Xavier, prominent mutant rights activist and founder of the safe-haven nation-island Krakoa, stands stoic in his argument for economic stability and strength for his people. Continuing with the extended metaphor of mutantkind to marginalized groups, Xavier argues in *House of X* that humans must accept that “[Krakoa’s] *sovereignty* will be recognized” (Hickman, 2021). This rewrites the narrative, allowing the historically disadvantaged Mutantkind to take institutional power into

their own hands. This storyline continues with the publishing of *Powers of X*, in which Max Eisenhardt (who will be discussed later) mentions that Krakoa's population "could be as high as two million," stating that they are not "ahead of [themselves]" but truly "woefully behind," thus clarifying the transition of institutional power from humans to people of their own, or more poetically, to a jury of their own peers (Hickman, 2021). Both of these stories prominently depict the intersection between identity and superheroes that is incredibly commonly found within the genre, as Christine Atchison, a frequent graphic novel blogger presents (Atchison, 2015). So, the banks and mega-corporations that typically work in direct opposition to Mutantkind (displaying economic and often class prejudice) will be no longer as they gain stability and security in their own right, pushing them towards liberation.

Falling Action

Following along the line of economics, it is incredibly important to realize that asking for change is not enough. There must be a systematic move towards this change. As Jenko writes about Elouise Cobell in her *A Small Measure of Justice*, even asking for help in the past and crying out for change is often not enough (Janko, 2013). Sometimes, success comes a lot later than it should. However, this liberation is deserved and depicts how one may succeed through harsh times. Although the Blackfeet's liberation was in an economic sense, there are multiple types of liberation. Another example of one of the less-explored forms of liberation is Volume 4, the 2023 edition of *Magneto*. The storyline follows Ashkenazi Jewish Max Eisenhardt, also known as Magneto. Volume 4 of *Magneto* delves deep into his background as a Holocaust survivor and his morals as well, showing how the metallokinetic Mutant acted to better help his kind (mutants in this case) avoid a fate similar to him. The story utilizes a voice-over style, allowing Eisenhardt to confront and rise above his horrors, framing his anger as a tool to be used

to better the future of others as he mentions he is able to “push aside trauma, longing, loss” for something greater (DeMatteis & Nauck, 2024). He is able to take over Xavier’s school as headmaster in his absence, and learns how to manage his liberation in a way that allows for future success and liberation for his people. Perhaps one of the more groundbreaking comic runs, *Immortal X-Men* written by prominent writer Kieron Gillen, argues for a more tangible kind of liberation: social and political liberation. Within the first issue of the series itself, Krakoa’s governing body is formed, indicating that Mutantkind has been able to place themselves in a relatively stable and safe environment, and are not only living well but *thriving* well (Gillen, 2022). This depicts that even groups that are historically marginalized can be granted peace if given the chance to take back power. Further in the same series, telepath and Mutant rights activist Emma Frost depicts the harshness of societal burdens and the pressure to perform. She mentions that she has to “be untouchably perfect, meaning that [she] never will be,” talking about the mask and persona she must put on in public as she holds multiple high positions within Krakoa society (Gillen, 2022). PhD Sarah M. Coyne with a specialization in psychology argues that this is especially common when looked at through a lens of gender bias, and states that depictions of female characters may impact children outside of their interaction with graphic-novel-based media (Coyne, 2014). Understanding this depicts that, even though liberation of one kind may be obtained, there is still opportunity to influence oneself from all the different prejudices that are built into our world, as many will still prevail.

Nuance

It is important to remember that there are numerous perspectives to look at a story within publication. There is a Doyleist perspective in which one looks at a story from a real-world perspective and a Watsonian perspective in which one looks at a story from an in-universe

perspective. Although the Watsonian perspective is arguably much more intriguing, it is important to remember to look at publication decisions through a Doyleist lens as well. For example, the *Sins Past* storyline arc depicted in *Amazing Spider-Man* is renowned for its mischaracterization and poor writing. Within the story, Gwen Stacy, a prominent love interest for Peter Parker's Spider-Man is essentially coerced into a sexual relationship with a primary antagonistic figure, the Green Goblin (Straczynski, 2006). However, the story is written as such that this is her choice, implying that her loyalty to Parker and her personality traits and character development were all for naught. Thankfully, the story was so poorly received, it was eventually declared retconned out. Perhaps one of the best depictions of an exact opposite story is *X-Men Red*, written by fan-favorite Al Ewing, a story that focuses on the Mutants of Mars (now called Arakko) and their status in the universe. Commonly seen as an intentional parallel to People of Color, Arakki Mutants are complex and nuanced characters that are able to hold their own. As the main character of the storyline, Storm (Ororo Munroe) is a Krakoaan Mutant who must prove herself to the Arakki before taking her place on the planet's governing body, indicating that Women of Color are able to have meaningful and nuanced stories that simultaneously depict the taking back of institutional power and the means of leveraging it for the bettering of her people (Ewing, 2022).

Conclusion

Marginalization is an incredibly impactful portion of the world we live in. While clearly detrimental to many individuals, marginalization is also a tenet upheld by institutions across our very globe. Though change is often something that people are fearful of, it is important to remember that we have only come to where we are today because of it, and we would be able to go much further if we continued to push the advent of accepting change. Graphic novels depict

this incredibly prominently, as change is almost always a major plot point in any story.

Throughout stories about marginalized individuals or extended metaphors about the very same group, graphic novels depict the multitude of lessons that are to be learned and applied to the real world. Thus, fiction remains to be seen as a reflection upon reality, and the lessons from one may be truly best served being reflected upon the other.

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